

TiGr-Nacre:

A New Damage-Tolerant
CFRP Composite

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Motivation

- Nacre: natural composite of brittle ceramic (95%) and biological polymer
- Composite toughness $\sim 9x$ higher than main constituent
- Toughening mechanisms:
 - Crack deflection
 - Tile pull-out (friction)
 - Damage diffusion

State of the art - CFRP

Exploiting nacre-inspired crack deflection mechanisms in CFRP via micro-structural design

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Crack deflection
Limited tile pull-out
No damage diffusion

How to achieve damage diffusion?

- State of the art for Nacre-CFRP
 - Carbon-fibre+epoxy tiles as analogs of ceramic in natural nacre
 - Neat epoxy as analog of polymer in natural nacre
- Requirements for damage diffusion:
 - Ductility – to maintain structural integrity once tiles slide / pull-out
 - Strain hardening – to prevent damage localisation at first site of initiation
- Solution:
 - Combine nacre micro-structure with TiGr fibre-metal laminate concept

Concept

Single CFRP layer with nacre structure

Created by laser-cutting uncured thin-ply (25 μm) prepreg

Lay-up: Combine Ti and CFRP

- 1 Nacre layer between 2 Ti layers
- Final lay-up: 21 Ti, 20 CF layers
- Tile patterns on either side of Ti layer offset by $\frac{1}{2}$ tile length
- Total Thickness = 1.1 mm
- Tiles interlock in-plane: friction maintains load transfer capacity
- Ti provides ductility and strain hardening

Experimental

- In-situ in SEM:
 - 3 point bend
 - 4 point bend
 - Deben micro-tester
 - 0.1 mm/min displacement rate
- Tensile test
 - 50 kN Instron test frame
 - 0.5 mm/min displacement rate

Results – 3 Point Bend

Force-displacement curve

Ductile failure behaviour

Load drops due to holding displacement while taking SEM images

Side view of specimen at 1.612 mm applied displacement

Ply buckling on compressive side

Tile pull-out and fracture on tensile side

Opening of cuts between tiles

Close-up view of damage mechanisms

Titanium layers still intact & bridging gaps between tiles

Necking of Ti layer indicating area of strain concentration

Fracture of tiles adjacent to opening cuts

Opening of cuts

Side view of specimen at 4.001 mm applied displacement

Complete tile pull-out on tensile side

Fracture of Ti layers
Damage zone 2-3 tile lengths wide (~1.5 mm)

Laminate still fluid tight

15.0kV 32.0mm x18 SE

3.00mm

Conclusions from 3 point bend

- Diffuse damage initiation, but size of process zone limited by concentrated load
- Still signs of damage diffusion, e.g. tiles pulled out at both ends
- Necking of Ti-layers indicates strain concentration, eventually leading to failure of the Ti-layer.
- Dissipative mechanisms observed:
 - Tile sliding pull-out, fibre fracture & pull-out, titanium plastic deformation due to tensile load, titanium micro-cracking, buckling inducing plastic deformation of titanium

Results - 4 point bend

Force-displacement curve

Ductile failure behaviour

Test ended due to reaching
limit of travel on test rig

Load drops due to holding
displacement while taking
SEM images

10.0kV 38.8mm x10 SE 5.00mm

Side view of specimen at 2.871 mm applied displacement

Buckling on compressive side

Tile pull-out initiating on tensile side

Close-up of damage initiation

Cuts between tiles opening along tensile side of specimen

Note large damage area

Zig-zag pattern due to tile pattern offset in 'adjacent' CFRP / nacre layers.

Tile fracture

Specimen side view at applied displacement of 6.001 mm

Note diffuse damage (tile pull-out) along entire lower portion of laminate. Titanium layers still intact

Zig-zag pattern due to offset in tile patterns in 'adjacent' nacre layers

Conclusions from 4 point bend

- Damage diffused throughout specimen. Process zone covers entire span between load application pins.
- Ductile behaviour
- Titanium layers remain intact: laminate is still fluid-tight

A black and white photograph showing a close-up of a composite material under stress. A diagonal crack runs from the top-left towards the bottom-right. The material is dark and fibrous. A bright, textured area, likely a fracture surface, is visible along the crack. The background is a light, textured surface.

Tensile tests

Tensile tests

Analysis in progress, results will be presented at the conference

Conclusions

Conclusions

- Created hybrid composite, combining TiGr FML with nacre-like microstructure
- Ductile behaviour, and damage diffusion through large process zone
- Under 4 point bend, process zone same size as constant moment region
- In 3 point bend, failure triggered by strain localisation in Ti layer
- Many energy-absorbing damage mechanisms observed, including:
tile pull-out, fibre pull-out, plastic deformation of titanium and titanium micro-cracking
- Fluid-tightness of laminate preserved even with large scale damage

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